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Research Article

Bio-analytical (RP-HPLC) Method Development and Validation for Levosulpiride from Human Plasma

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ABSTRACT

A robust and sensitive reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the quantitative determination of Levosulpiride in human plasma. The study aimed to facilitate accurate and reliable bioanalytical evaluation of Levosulpiride for pharmacokinetic, bioavailability, and bioequivalence assessments. The chromatographic method was optimized using a Quality by Design (QbD) approach, with a mobile phase consisting of ammonium formate buffer and methanol (28.19:71.81 v/v), and detection at 287 nm using a Waters Bridge C18 column. The method demonstrated a retention time of approximately 5.51 minutes and exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 10–50 µg/mL. Bioanalytical validation was performed in accordance with ICH guidelines, confirming the method's selectivity, specificity, accuracy, precision, robustness, and stability. The method showed high recovery rates (~99.94%) and low relative standard deviations, indicating its reproducibility and reliability. Stability studies, including freeze-thaw, short-term, and long-term storage conditions, confirmed the stability of Levosulpiride in plasma samples. This validated RP-HPLC method offers a simple, cost-effective, and sensitive analytical tool suitable for routine quality control, pharmacokinetic studies, and clinical monitoring of Levosulpiride, with significant improvements over previously reported methods in terms of efficiency and simplicity.

INTRODUCTION

In the development of modern pharmaceuticals, accurate and reliable measurement of drug

concentrations in biological matrices is essential for determining pharmacokinetic profiles, assessing bioavailability, and establishing bioequivalence. Bio analytical methods,

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particularly those utilizing high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), play a critical role in this domain by enabling the quantitative determination of drugs and their metabolites in biological fluids such as plasma, urine, and saliva. Bioavailability refers to the rate and extent to which an active pharmaceutical ingredient becomes available at the site of action after administration, while bioequivalence signifies the absence of a significant difference in the bioavailability between two pharmaceutical products under similar conditions. Reliable assessment of these parameters requires precise analytical techniques and validated methodologies. The complexity of biological matrices such as blood plasma presents significant challenges in drug analysis. Hence, method development involves the careful selection of extraction procedures, chromatographic conditions, and detection settings. Commonly employed extraction techniques include protein precipitation, liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), and solid-phase extraction (SPE), each offering specific advantages and limitations depending on the physicochemical properties of the analyte and the matrix involved. Sample preparation is a crucial step that aims to isolate the drug from interfering substances while maintaining its stability and recoverability. The quantification of

drug levels in plasma is often used as a surrogate marker for tissue concentrations, enabling the monitoring and optimization of therapeutic regimens. In this context, Levosulpiride—a substituted benzamide antipsychotic and prokinetic agent—requires robust analytical techniques to ensure precise measurement in plasma samples for clinical and pharmacokinetic studies. Bioanalytical method validation ensures that the method is suitable for its intended purpose, emphasizing parameters such as selectivity, accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and stability. Full, partial, and cross-validations are conducted depending on the study design and regulatory requirements. RP-HPLC (Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography) has become a preferred analytical tool due to its reproducibility, sensitivity, and suitability for complex matrices. The present study focuses on the development and validation of a robust and sensitive RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Levosulpiride in human plasma. The validated method is expected to be applicable for routine drug analysis in bioavailability and bioequivalence studies, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards and contributing to the safe and effective therapeutic use of Levosulpiride.

Drug Profile

Name	Levosulpiride
Description	Levosulpiride, sold under the brand name Neoprad is a substituted benzamide antipsychotic, reported to be a selective antagonist of dopamine D2 receptor activity on both central and peripheral levels. It is an atypical neuroleptic and a prokinetic agent. Levosulpiride is also claimed to have mood elevating properties.
Structure	<p>The chemical structure of Levosulpiride consists of a benzamide core. The benzene ring is substituted with a sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH₂) at the para position and a methoxy group (-OCH₃) at the ortho position. The amide group (-CONH-) is attached to the benzene ring and is further linked to a 2-ethylpyrrolidine ring system.</p>

Fig No.1.1 Structure of Levosulpiride

CAS NO	23672-07-3
Molecular Formula	C ₁₅ H ₃ N ₃ O ₄ S
Molecular Weight	341.43 g/mol
Mono isotopic Mass	340.92 g/mol
IUPAC Name	N-[[[(2S)-(-)-1-Ethylpyrrolidin-2-yl]methyl]-2-methoxy-5-sulfamoylbenzamide
Category	Levosulpiride is an a antipsychotic used mainly in the treatment atypical neuroleptic and a prokinetic agent.
Colour	White Powder
pka	10.24 (strongest acidic) 8.39 (Strongest Basic)
Melting point	183-186 °C
Storage	Store at room temperature away from light and moisture.
Uses	Levosulpiride is used in the treatment of: Psychoses, particularly negative symptoms of schizophrenia, anxiety disorders, dysthymia,

Literature Survey:

Sr. No.	Reference	Type of Work Done	Conclusion
1	Nivedeetha Halekote Shivaraju, et.al.	Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Pantoprazole And Levosulpiride In Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: 10 mM ammonium acetate (pH 4.0 adjusted using acetic acid): Acetonitrile in the ratio of 20:80% v/v Column: C18 column Kromasil (250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm) Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min. Detection Wavelength: 241 nm. Temp: 25° C
2	Raghu Khimani, et.al.	Development and Validation of HPLC Method for determination of Ilaprazole and Levosulpride	Mobile Phase: 10 mM Ammonium acetate in water, pH 5.0: Diluent in proportion of ratio 45:55%V/v Column: C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 mcm) Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min. Temp: 25° C
3	K.SENTHILNATHAN, et.al.	Method Development And Validation For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Esomeprazole And Levosulpiride By Using RPHPLC In Its Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: Buffer and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 32;68 Column: ODS (150mm 4.6mm, 5µ) Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min. Detection Wavelength: 290 nm. Temp: 25° C
4	Daniel Gonzalez, et.al.	Simultaneous determination of Levosulpiride and sulfamethoxazole in dried plasma and urine spots	Levosulpiride-sulfamethoxazole (TMP-SMX) is an antimicrobial drug combination commonly prescribed in children and adults. The study objectives were to validate and apply an HPLC-MS/MS method to

			quantify TMP-SMX in dried plasma spots (DPS) and dried urine spots (DUS), and perform a comparability analysis with liquid matrices
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MATERIAL AND METHOD

1. Preparation of Phosphate Buffer Solution

6.8 gm of Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in sufficient water (HPLC grade) with aid of sonicator. Then add triethylamine or orthophosphoric acid was used to adjust the pH to 5.

2. Preparation of stock solutions

10 mg of Levosulpiride diluted with 10mL Methanol in volumetric flask to get concentration of 1000 µg/ml. From the resulting solution 0.1 ml was diluted to 10 ml with Methanol to obtain concentration of 10 µg/ml of Levosulpiride.

3. Selection of detection wavelength

From the standard stock solution further dilutions were done using water and scanned over the range of 200-400 nm and the spectra were overlain. It was observed that drug showed considerable absorbance at 287 nm.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

According to the above prescribed, the RP-HPLC method was developed and validated as per ICH guideline with the QbD approach. It is first stated the application of Quality by design approach to Bioanalytical method development and validation. Optimized mobile phase by design expert software was used to estimate drug in human plasma. Details are as follows.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Mobile phase: Ammonium format buffer: Methanol (28.19:71.81v/v), pH of buffer: 3, Analytical column: Cis column Waters XBridge (4.6x 250mm id. particle size 5µm), UV detection: 287 nm, Injection volume: 10 µL., Flow rate: 1.00 mL. min, Temperature: Ambient, Run time: 10 min.

Preparation of spiked plasma samples

To each Eppendorf tube add required amount of Levosulpiride. Add 100 µL of plasma to it. Then add 100 µL acetonitrile as a precipitating agent to it and allow vortex for 5 min. To get Proper mixture of above solution, centrifuge it for 15 min at 2000 rpm. Subject it under nitrogen gas for concentration and separate supernatant in Eppendorf tubes. 20 µL of the supernatant was the final resulting sample.

System Suitability Parameter

Following are the parameters when taken results of samples of spiked plasma.

Table 1.1: Peak Properties of Chromatogram of Levosulpiride Esylate (10u/ml)

Sr. No.	Parameters	Observation
1.	Retention time	5.513 min
2.	Peak area	84852
3.	Theoretical plates	19145

Figure 1.2: Chromatogram of Levosulpiride Esylate spiked in human plasma (10µg/ml)

Bioanalytical Validation

1) Selectivity

For selectivity, the blank samples of the plasma were obtained from six different persons. Each blank sample was tested for interference in the Levosulpiride peak. The plasma and Levosulpiride

peak were well resolved. It was found that the peak from blank plasma does not interfere with the peak of Levosulpiride. Hence developed method is selective and the peak obtained at 5.5min is only because of Levosulpiride Esylate.

Blank (Spiked Plasma)

Figure 1.3: A typical chromatogram of blank human plasma

Sample 1

Figure 1.4: Chromatogram of Levosulpiride Esylate spiked in human plasma (10µg/ml)

2) Linearity

Linearity of the Bioanalytical method is the capability to obtain responses which are directly proportional to the concentration of drug

molecule. Linearity of Levosulpiride Esylate was employed from 10µg/mL. to 50µg/mL. The concentration range was found to be linear and results of slope and correlation coefficient were found to be acceptable.

Table 1.2: Results of Linearity

Sr. No	Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak Area	Peak Properties	Retention Time	Asymmetric Factor	Theoretical Plates
1.	10	84352		5.514	1.151	19163
2.	20	161504		5.514	1.153	19147
3.	30	251456		5.514	1.157	19200
4.	40	344408		5.514	1.151	19108
5.	50	421260		5.514	1.155	19197

3) Precision

Table 1.3: System Precision results for Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. No	Concentration µg/ml	Intraday Precision Peak Area	Interday Precision Peak Area	Repeatability
1.	10	84627	84536	84124
2.	10	84122	85641	84279
3.	10	84794	85647	84877
4.	10	84261	85982	84934
5.	10	85552	85461	85655
6.	10	84764	85344	84165
Average		84686.67	85435.17	84672.33
Standard Deviation		460.05	447.91	546.00
RSD%		0.543	0.524	0.644

4) Specificity

In a selectivity study, we have demonstrated that the peak of Levosulpiride Esylate is resolved

efficiently in human plasma. amount of drug vered was found to be 99.94%.

Table 1.4: Recovery results of Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sample	Label Claim (mg)	Amount of Drug Found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Retention Time (min)
Capsule	100	99.94	99.94	5.514

5) Repeatability

Table 1.5: Repeatability results for Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. no	Concentration ug/ml	Peak Area
1.	10	84124
2.	10	84279
3.	10	84877
4.	10	84934
5.	10	85655
6.	10	84165
Mean		84672.33
Std. Dev.		546.00
%RSD		0.644

Relative Standard Deviation	0.488.
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Wavelength

Table 1.7: Results of Robustness (Wavelength) for Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. No	Parameter	Response
Detection Wavelength (nm)		Peak Area
1	391	84016
2	392 (Optimized)	84694
3	393	84219
Relative Standard Deviation		0.33369

6) Robustness

Mobile Phase

Table 1.6: Results of Robustness (Mobile Phase) for Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. No	Parameter	Response
Buffer: Methanol (V/V)		Retention Time (min)
1	30:70	5.590
2	29: 71 (Optimized)	5.564
3	28:72	5.524

pH of mobile phase

Table 1.8: Results of Robustness (pH) for Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. No	Parameter	Response
pH of Buffer (mmol/L)		Peak Area
1	2.8	85219
2	3 (Optimized)	85698
3	3.2	85348
Relative Standard Deviation		0.236

7) Recovery

Table 1.9: Recovery results of Levosulpiride by RP-HPLC

Sr. No	Amount of Sample (µg/ml)	Amount of Drug Added (µg/ml)	Amount of Drug Recovered (µg/ml)	Recovery %
1	10	8	7.99	99.87
2	10	10	9.98	99.80
3	10	12	12.01	100.08

8) Stability of Levosulpiride in Human Plasma

The objective of this study was to determine the stability of Levosulpiride in human plasma. We

interpreted the storage conditions by studying freeze and thaw, short term, long term and stock solution stability.

1. Freeze and Thaw Stability

The stability of Levosulpiride was determined in spiked plasma by three freeze-thaw cycles at - 20 deg * C = 1 deg * C After comparing the Stability samples with freshly prepared samples and concluded that the drug remains stable in the freeze/thaw cycles.

Table 1.10: Results of Freeze and Thaw Stability

Replicate No.	Actual Concentratio			
	LQC (8 µg/ml)		HQC (24 µg/ml)	
	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample
1	67526	68952	203105	210132
2	68497	67963	206586	206988
3	67349	67198	201489	205266
Mean	67790	68037	203726	207462
SD	504.65	718.01	2126.76	2014.61
% RSD	0.744	1.055	1.043	0.9710

2. Short Term Stability

The spiked plasma samples were estimated for 8 hours stored at room temperature. Comparing

stability samples against the freshly prepared spiked quality control samples assessed stability..

Table 1.11: Results of Short-Term Stability

Replicate No.	Actual Concentratio			
	LQC (2 µg/ml)		HQC (60 µg/ml)	
	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample
1	16433	16425	503947	500385
2	16513	16654	507976	517196
3	16351	16942	500159	501729
Mean	16432.33	16673.67	504027.3	506436.7
SD	66.13	211.52	3191.78	7627.7
% RSD	0.402	1.268	0.633	1.506

3. Long Term Stability

A sample of spiked plasma was determined for 7 days stored at room temperature, comparing them

against the freshly weighed stock solution assessed for stability.

Table 1.12: Results of Long-Term Stability

Replicate No.	Actual Concentratio			
	LQC (8 µg/ml)		HQC (24 µg/ml)	
	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample	Comparison Sample	Stability Sample
1	68462	67394	201894	214665
2	68116	69421	208962	217642
3	69923	67287	202119	214874

Mean	68833.6	68034	204325	215727
SD	783	981.7	3280	1356
% RSD	1.137	1.442	1.605	0.628

CONCLUSION

Our current experiment illustrates the development and validation of a simple, rapid, and very sensitive RP-HPLC method and Bioanalytical method developed for the determination of Levosulpiride in pure form, dosage forms, and in spiked human plasma. This developed experiment overcomes the drawbacks that have been found in the other reported method where no need to use the isocratic method, more retention time, and complex extraction for this simple method. Also, this method is money-saving as it needs less expensive instrumentations, solvents, and reagents. The high accuracy, precision, and sensitivity make this simple method be a reliable and reproducible method to be applied in quality control, Quality assurance as well as pharmacokinetic analysis of Levosulpiride Esylate

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